

Computational study of mesh-structured triboelectric generators

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ABSTRACT

Triboelectric generators (TEGs) are vital for transforming mechanical energy into electrical power, facilitating the creation of self-powered devices that minimize reliance on traditional power sources. Furthermore, most typical TEGs are limited to simple 2D forms and films, limiting their potential applications. We have focused on developing 3D architectures with volumetric triboelectric dipoles to solve this. To this end, two polymeric materials with different triboelectric properties were employed for the designing of 3D architectures and the optimization of all-polymer TEG performance. Our simplified design eliminates the integration of internal electrodes in a 3D structure. This study paves the way towards volumetric 3D TEG architectures for improved mechanical energy harvesting.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent developments of additive technology for printing of 3-dimensional (3D) structures include the synthesis and development of 3D-printable biodegradable triboelectric materials^{1,2} for applications in triboelectric generators (TEGs), which can be regarded as a significant contribution towards the sustainability of portable electronics industry. Moreover, a number of solutions have been developed for mechanical energy harvesting using 3D printing of diverse structures³ ranging from rigid to flexible and stretchable structures. For flexible hinge structures, in particular, a number of promising solutions have been proposed due to facilitating large displacements yet providing conditions for minimum wear. Among these, auxetic metamaterials could be distinguished as a possible approach for scalable mesh structures which offer advantages in terms of multifunctionality by combining energy harvesting or sensing with structural⁴ or mechanical energy absorption^{5,6} functions. However, the optimality of energy harvesting of the said metamaterial structures has been mostly investigated in terms of the effects of homogeneity of deformations, while fairly limited insights have been gained regarding the sensitivities of the structural parameters and the geometrical transitions between the proposed structures and conventional structures serving as references of lower dimensional limit⁷. The importance of the latter could be most clearly observed by considering that for most of the above cited structures, the motion components that are pertinent to contact electrification (CE) can be effectively reduced to 1-dimensional (1D) contact-separation (CS) motion.

Consequently, the aim of the presented study is to numerically develop periodic metamaterial-like structures which would be optimal for combined energy harvesting and structural material applications. For this purpose, structures with both negative and near-zero Poisson ratios were investigated. In particular, the choice⁸ of structures with negative and near-zero Poisson ratios was

motivated by their potential advantages for high deformability and conformability. Moreover, according to the findings of published studies^{5,9-11}, a correlation between the efficiency of lattice-type TEG structures and their effective Poisson's ratio could be anticipated. Furthermore, according to the results of an earlier studies^{12, 13}, multi-layer TEG structures may provide higher performance if appropriate thickness scaling is applied. The latter effect has been largely attributed to the enhanced alignment of internal dipoles within the volume of the triboelectric materials. Consequently, an analogous effect can be anticipated for the periodic lattice based structures that are investigated in this study.

To address the considerations outlined above, critical structural parameters for triboelectric energy harvesting performance were explored for each structure. In particular, for interpretation of the conceptual relation of the effects of selected parameters with more conventional TEG structures, comparisons with analogous single- and multi-bilayer structures with parallel contact surfaces were performed. Moreover, since multi-bilayer TEGs have been proposed as efficient solutions for volumetric energy harvesting¹³, the presently studied structures may be regarded as an extension of the said approach.

2 METHOD

For theoretical comparisons of the considered lattices, the approach of voltage-charge-displacement relation was adapted^{14, 15}. To this end, peak power (P_{\max}) and average power (P_{avg}) responses of the selected structural parameters were estimated according to $V_{OC}(x)$ and $Q_{SC}(x)$ relations (V_{OC} – open circuit voltage, Q_{SC} – short circuit charge, x – contact-separation displacement coordinate), which were obtained from electrostatic Finite Element Method (FEM) simulations of the lattices, performed using COMSOL¹⁶. The external load was defined by an electrical resistance parameter (R), which was optimized according to the peak and average power criteria above.

Due to extruded type lattices being investigated, 2-dimensional (2D) structures were employed for the FEM simulations. As an additional simplification, the deformation of the lattices was modelled as ideal hinge based. Further, for assessing the dynamic current responses of the lattices, a smoothed step function (1) was employed for defining a numerically simulated separation displacement for a duration of 0.025 ms (sample response shown in Figure S 1).

$$\begin{cases} x = x_{\max} \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \cos \left(\frac{\pi v}{x_{\max}} t \right) \right), & (t < \frac{x_{\max}}{v}) \\ x = x_{\max}, & (t \geq \frac{x_{\max}}{v}) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where v – nominal velocity of vertical separation of the contact surfaces (0.3 m/s applied). For the simulations, x_{\max} values were determined by the applicable geometric parameters of the lattices.

For defining the simulated active materials, the dielectric properties of known triboelectric materials^{17, 18} were applied. In particular, poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) (dielectric constant of 2.4¹⁹) was used as a electronegative triboelectric material, whereas polyamide 66 (PA66) (dielectric constant of 3.6²⁰) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) (dielectric constant of 2.9²¹) were employed as electropositive triboelectric materials in Section 3.1 and 3.2, respectively. Further, a value of 10^6 was assumed as an approximation of infinity value of a dielectric constant for metals, used as electrodes. The simulated surface charge density of triboelectric contact surfaces was defined either as a value corresponding to the limit of air breakdown, obtainable, e.g., by ion injection²² (2.4×10^{-10} C/mm² in Section 3.1), or a value that would be compatible with contact electrification of the simulated triboelectric materials¹⁸ (1×10^{-11} C/mm² in Section 3.2). In view of 3D printing limitations, the thickness of all layers of active

materials was set as 1 mm. A maximum tilt angle of 45 deg was applied to all plate elements unless noted otherwise.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Comparison of 2-dimensionally periodic TEG lattices in parametric limit cases

Theoretical simulations were performed in order to identify the most promising lattice topologies for 3D-printable, volumetric TEG applications. A comparison was performed for rhombic and tilted/displaced cell lattices (Figure 1 (B, C)) against the respective values of a parallel plate structure reference (Figure 1 (A)). For all the lattices, identical parallel-plate contact configurations were obtained in the maximum compression state. For the tilted/displaced lattice, however, the reciprocal motion was defined such that the tilt angle would remain non-zero until contact between the approaching surfaces would be reached. Thereby, maximum advantage could be taken of the subsequent sliding between the contact surfaces due to rotation. Two-cell vertical expansion was applied as a minimum setting for including the effect of periodicity along the second axis of the periodic cells. The boundary conditions in the horizontal direction were defined as periodic. A length (L) of 10 mm was applied to all plate elements unless noted otherwise. For all plots of the parametric analysis, the set of tested parameter values was adjusted in accordance with any nonlinearities observed with the initial sets of uniformly distributed parameter values.

Figure 1. Schematic depiction of periodic unit cells of parallel plates (A), rhombic (tilted plates) (B), and tilted and vertically displaced plates (C) based TEG lattices (blue and orange designate materials of opposite triboelectric polarity)

During analysis of the results that were obtained using the assumed maximum achievable density of CE charge ($2.4 \times 10^{-10} \text{ C/mm}^2$ as discussed in Section 2) it was observed that the maximum open circuit voltage would exceed the air breakdown voltage according to the Paschen's relation²². Although according to the above cited experimental study it could be assumed that in some cases short circuit gap voltage could be more relevant for determining the breakdown stability of a TEG, for further analysis of the results, $1/10$ of the initially defined CE charge density (i.e., $2.4 \times 10^{-11} \text{ C/mm}^2$) was assumed such that the Paschen's relation would not be violated, up to an order of magnitude, either for open circuit voltage based comparisons. To this end, it was verified by test calculations (Figure S 2) that the linear scaling of transferred charge, current, and voltage, and the invariance of the optimum resistance with respect to the variation of the CE charge density, which has been proven analytically for flat plate TEGs¹⁴, holds also for a non-planar (rhombic) lattice. Consequently, it could be concluded that all the said quantities could be linearly scaled for the CE charge density of interest if, at least, compatible lattices were considered. Likewise, the respective power responses could be scaled quadratically with respect to the CE charge density due to power (calculated as the product of current and voltage) being quadratically dependent on the transferred CE charge. It should be added

that the latter scaling properties imply that, effectively, structural optimization of such TEGs is independent of the CE charge density as long as it can be treated as a pure material and surface property¹⁴.

For the rhombic lattice (Figure 1 (B)), the effect of maximum separation (x_{max}) and maximum tilt angle (α_{max}) parameters was investigated to identify the structure parameters for best possible electromechanical output for proposed 3D structures. For the maximum separation parameter (with a constant maximum tilt angle of 45 deg), an optimum value of around 15 mm could be identified according to the power responses (Figure 2 (A)), which are observed to partially correlate with the short circuit charge density (Figure 2 (B)). The optimum value was attributed to a balance between increasing voltage (Figure 2 (B)) and decreasing maximum current density values (Figure 2 (C)). For the maximum tilt angle parameter, analogous responses were estimated with an optimum value of x_{max} above. The obtained theoretical optimum values of power correspond to the minimum angle limit and approach the reference value of parallel plate structure (Figure 3 (A)). The value is attributed to decreasing voltage values with respect to the parameter (Figure 3 (B)) and a relatively small change in charge densities (Figure 3 (C)) as well as the short circuit charge (Figure 3 (B)). Importantly, for the maximum tilt parameter case, the applied x_{max} and v values for the referenced parallel plate structure was adjusted to 6.6 mm and 0.1 m/s, respectively, according to the effective maximum separation between regions of maximum and minimum voltage (Figure S 3).

Figure 2. Peak and average power (A), open circuit voltage and short circuit charge density (B), and peak current density (C) (current density corresponds to peak power and average power optimized external load resistances) with respect to the maximum separation parameter of a rhombic lattice

Figure 3. Peak and average power (A), open circuit voltage and short circuit charge density (B), and peak current density (C) (current density corresponds to peak power and average power optimized external load resistances) with respect to the maximum tilt angle parameter of a rhombic lattice

Analogous parametric responses were obtained for the tilted and vertically displaced lattice (Figure 1 (C)). For the variation of maximum separation parameter (rhombic part x_r excluded), in particular, a convergence of power responses at the maximum parameter limit is observed (Figure 4 (A)). Consequently, although the shapes of voltage, short circuit charge (Figure 4 (B)), and current density (Figure 4 (C)) responses are qualitatively similar to those of the rhombic lattice (Figure 3 (B, C)), a difference with the peaked power response of the latter (Figure 3 (A)) can be distinguished. The difference can thereby be interpreted as a result of rotational component of the contact surface motion of the rhombic lattice. At variance, the monotonic increase of power responses for the tilted and vertically displaced lattices may be attributed to structural similarity with parallel plates based TEG in view of relatively similar respective power responses (Figure 4 (A)). Further, the parametric response of tilt angle was estimated for an optimum value of the maximum separation parameter, estimated as the minimum convergence value of the parameter (about 17 mm) according to Figure 4 (A). Similar to the rhombic lattice, a convergence towards the reference value of parallel plates is observed for all the obtained responses at the limit of small tilt angle (Figure 5). It is noted that, in distinction to the rhombic lattice, no adjustment of the maximum separation parameter was performed for the parallel plates due to the separation of tilt and linear displacement motions in this case. Furthermore, the nonlinearity of the power responses (Figure 4 (A)) is observed to correlated with the respective voltage response (Figure 4 (B)), which indicates an increase at large tilt values, in distinction to the decreasing voltage response of the rhombic lattice (Figure 3 (B)). The latter difference can be attributed to an increase of the maximum separation between the charged

surfaces at larger tilt angles due to the rhombic component (x_r in Figure 1 (C)) in the case of tilted and vertically displaced lattice, and a constant value of maximum charge separation on the case of rhombic lattice. In addition to the tilt and displacement parameters, analogous parametric responses were obtained for the plate length (L) parameter, since for the tilted and vertically displaced lattice it could be regarded as an independent geometric parameter. For this parameter, a peaked response with an optimum L value at around 10 mm was observed for power response (Figure 6 (A)) as well as voltage and, to a lesser extent, short circuit charge (Figure 6 (B)) responses. At variance, the convergence of current density responses to the respective values of parallel plates at large L limit (Figure 6 (C)) can be interpreted as determined by geometric similarity, similar to the convergence cases above, and by a relatively small variation of the short circuit charge (Figure 6 (B)).

Figure 4. Peak and average power (A), open circuit voltage and short circuit charge density (B), and peak current density (C) (current density corresponds to peak power and average power optimized external load resistances) with respect to the maximum separation parameter of a tilted and vertically displaced lattice

Figure 5. Peak and average power (A), open circuit voltage and short circuit charge density (B), and peak current density (C) (current density corresponds to peak power and average power optimized external load resistances) with respect to the maximum tilt angle parameter of a tilted and vertically displaced lattice

Figure 6. Peak and average power (A), open circuit voltage and short circuit charge density (B), and peak current density (C) (current density corresponds to peak power and average power optimized external load resistances) with respect to the plate length parameter of a tilted and vertically displaced lattice

3.2 Comparison of finite TEG lattices of different Poisson ratios

Within the framework of flat platelets and flexible hinges based lattices of maximum contact surfaces, two alternatives of finite-sized lattices – zero (ZPR) (Figure 1 (B)) and negative valued (NPR) (Figure 7) Poisson ratio – were compared using parallel plates based structure (Figure 1 (A)) as a reference. For all lattices, flat plate equivalent dimensions of about 80 mm along the horizontal axis (corresponding to the compressed state, spaces excluded) and about 60 mm along the vertical axis (corresponding to a maximum displacement of about 57 mm) were applied. Consequently, by changing the periodic cell expansion parameter (n_{exp}), the effects of cells scaling or changing the equivalent flat plate cell density could be studied.

Figure 7. Schematic depiction of periodic unit cell of a TEG lattice with a negative Poisson ratio (blue and orange designate materials of opposite triboelectric charge)

The obtained results for averaged power responses (Figure 8 (A, B)) indicate a correlation of power values with the respective voltage values (Figure 8 (C)). Since no correlation is observed with the average short circuit charge (Figure 9 (A)) and current responses (Figure 9 (B), Figure 10) for the ZPR lattice, it may be concluded that voltage is the main contributing factor to the power response of the particular lattice. At variance, the reduction of short circuit charge and current responses can be regarded as an explanation for the reduction of power responses of NPR and parallel plate lattices (Figure 8) despite a small increase in the respective voltage values (Figure 8 (C)).

According to the obtained voltage responses (Figure 8 (C)) the peaked response of the ZPR lattice at around $n_{exp} = 4$ should be pointed out as a qualitative difference with respect to the monotonic responses of the NPR and parallel plate lattices. The difference can be attributed to two main contributing factors. The first lies in the part of steep increase of the response of ZPR voltage, which can be linked to the nonlinear change in effective volumetric density of charged surfaces with respect to the expansion parameter and to deviations from the exact Poisson ratio of zero due to the finite size effect, which manifests on the outer vertical sides of the lattices. The nonlinear change, in turn, is due to shrinking proportion of non-contacting outer side surfaces, which is at variance with the linear increase of charged surfaces for the NPR and parallel plate lattices (Figure 11, Figure 12). The second is assumed to be related to the decrease of the voltage of the ZPR lattice in distinction to the increase of the voltage of NPR and parallel plate lattices for the n_{exp} values above the ZPR voltage maximum. The difference is attributed to corresponding differences in voltage distributions (Figure 12) of the lattices at decreasing distances between the contact surfaces. For the ZPR lattice, reduced interactions between arrays of adjacent vertical cells in the lattice are obtained due to increasing distances between the respective arrays (Figure 12 (A)). This is at variance with the NPR lattice, for which shrinking distances between adjacent vertical arrays occur as a result of the negative Poisson ratio (Figure 12 (C)). Furthermore, for the parallel plate lattice, no compatible effects can be distinguished due to a single (vertical) axis expansion of periodic cells being applicable instead of the 2D expansion of ZPR and NPR lattices (Figure 12 (C)).

Figure 8. Peak power (A), average power (B), and open circuit voltage (C) with respect to the cell expansion parameter of NPR ($v < 0$), ZPR ($v = 0$), and parallel plate lattices

Figure 9. Short circuit charge density (A) and short circuit current (B) with respect to the cell expansion parameter of NPR ($v < 0$), ZPR ($v = 0$), and parallel plate lattices

Figure 10. Peak current densities that correspond to (A) peak power and (B) average power optimized external load resistances: response with respect to the cell expansion parameter of NPR ($v < 0$), ZPR ($v = 0$), and parallel plate lattices

Figure 11. Short circuit voltage (mV) distribution at maximum (left column) and minimum (right column) separation of contact surfaces of (A) ZPR, (B) NPR, and (C) parallel plate lattices with a single periodic cell expansion

Figure 12. Short circuit voltage (mV) distribution at maximum (left column) and minimum (right column) separation of contact surfaces of (A) ZPR, (B) NPR, and (C) parallel plate lattices with an eight periodic cell expansion

Further, a similar rate of reduction of the current for the ZPR and NPR lattices (Figure 10). For the parallel plate lattice, however, a less pronounced reduction of current was observed despite the respective short circuit responses (Figure 9) being qualitatively similar. The difference may be

regarded as a result of both short circuit charge and current responses of the parallel plates lattice being higher than those of ZPR and NPR lattices (Figure 9). Also, in view of the corresponding separation distance dependent charge densities of the lattices (Figure 13), the difference may be interpreted as a result of gradient of charge density with respect to separation (x) of the parallel plate lattice being notably higher than those of the ZPR and NPR lattices. Additionally, it is noted that for all the considered lattices, a possible correlation is observed between the short circuit current (Figure 9 (B)) and the average gradient of charge density with respect to separation (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Short circuit charge density with respect to the separation between outer contact surfaces of NPR, ZPR, and parallel plate lattices with 1-cell (A) and 8-cell (B) periodic expansions

3.3 Discussion

In view of the results of earlier experimental studies on multi-layered TEG structures^{12, 13} and a combined experimental and computational study reporting the possibility of the formation of nonlinear potential distributions due to CE²³, the reduction of the predicted power response of all the considered lattice types with increasing numbers of layers could be interpreted as an indication of the significance of dipole reorientation which may not have been fully captured by the current, linear electrostatic TEG model. Moreover, subtle differences in screening behavior, which can be relevant in cases of triboelectric contacts with a conductor²⁴ or for contacts in the presence of different gaseous species²⁵, also have not been considered by the present model. Nonetheless, alternative, application-tailored variations of the structures could be considered within the framework of the present computational model. One such possibility could be identified with treating each individual pair of contact surfaces as a separate TEG for sensing applications. Alternatively, arrays of parallel-connected TEGs²⁶ could be formed for purposes of microscale energy harvesting. Thus, advantage could be taken of the maximum achievable volumetric charge density. Another approach consists in deploying layer alignments that would conceptually correspond to multi-layer versions of double-sided TEGs. Thereby, advantages due to simplicity of single electrode TEGs could be implemented in a scalable and efficient manner²⁷. Further modification approaches could involve the addition of parallel flat surface elements, which would be particularly relevant for low deformation sensing applications²⁸.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions could be drawn from the theoretical study:

- Nonlinear, decreasing power responses with respect to periodic cell refinement indicate that under the restrictions of the present model, other performance characteristics could be relevant for deploying the studied lattice structures

- For periodic structures of decreasing cell sizes, the auxetic lattice yields the most pronounced improvement in terms of open circuit voltage
- None of the considered structures indicates an increase of current due to refined periodic cell sizes, which may explain the observed reduction of power values
- With further structural or cell connection scheme modifications, maximum volumetric charge density could be potentially taken advantage of in application-tailored manner

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6 DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, O.V., upon request.

7 REFERENCES

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Figure S 1. Sample response of a two plates based TEG with an external resistance of $1e10 \Omega$: (a) imposed displacement, (b) open circuit voltage and internal capacitance, (c) transferred and short circuit charge, (d) current, (e) voltage, and (f) power density

Figure S 2. Peak and average power (a), open circuit voltage and short circuit charge density (b), peak current density (c) (current density corresponds to peak power and average power optimized external load resistances), and optimum external load resistance (d) (corresponds to peak power and average power optimized values) with respect to the CE charge density of a rhombic lattice

Figure S 3. Open circuit voltage (mV) distribution of a rhombic lattice